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Research Article

A Cross-Sectional Study of Knowledge, Attitude, And Practice of ADR And Pharmacovigilance Among Diploma in Pharmacy Students in Manipur, India

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ABSTRACT

All drugs come with some harmful side effects. Most of them are minor effects however, some drugs can cause serious harmful effects which can lead to negative health impact. Hence all drugs that are in the market are needed to monitor their effects. It can be done through reporting of adverse drug reaction (ADR) to any of the pharmacovigilance centre. For this, the knowledge, attitude and practice of health care professionals toward ADR and pharmacovigilance is a must. The present study was performed to assess the knowledge, attitude and practice toward ADR reporting by diploma pharmacy students. A questionnaire was distributed and the response was analysed using descriptive statistical method. The participants had good knowledge on ADR and pharmacovigilance. 92% of the participants were aware with the term pharmacovigilance and 72.6% of them know that ADR can be reported directly. The attitude of the participants was found to be good. 91.9% participants think that ADR reporting is necessary and 98.6% participants think it will ensure patient safety. 50% of the participants had received training on ADR reporting and 77.5% are willing to report ADR in the future. It was concluded that the pharmacy students displayed relatively good knowledge and positive attitude but insufficient practice regarding ADRs and pharmacovigilance. There is a need for continuous awareness and learning strategy for the pharmacists and to emphasise the importance for active participation in the pharmacovigilance process for a safety and improve quality of life for the patient.

INTRODUCTION

By diagnosing, mitigating, treating, or preventing disease through physiological or psychological

change, medications are used to cure a disease state and lessen symptoms related to the disorder. As a result, it ensures that a patient's health improves and that their quality of life is improved.

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Both short-term and long-term use are possible. Although clinical trials are used to determine the safety and efficacy of medications and vaccines before they are marketed, unintended side effects and toxicities are always possible. When these products are used, they might occasionally result in unanticipated and unwanted side effects known as adverse medication reactions (ADRs).^{1,2,3} Adverse drug reactions (ADRs) are defined by the World Health Organization as “Any response caused by a drug that is unintentional, noxious, and takes place at the drug doses which are used for diagnosing, prophylaxis, or treatment of a disease or due to the medications for the physiological functions.”^{4,5,6,7} One of the main causes of morbidity and a significant financial strain on health care resources are adverse drug reactions, or ADRs. According to reports, adverse responses account between 2.4% to 6.5% of all hospital admissions, many of which can be avoided. India has a 6.7% incidence of severe ADRs.⁸ ADRs may cause short-term or long-term harm, disability, or death; they may necessitate stopping the medication, altering the drug's therapy, changing the dosage, requiring hospitalization or a prolonged stay in a medical facility; they may require supportive treatment; they may make diagnosis much more difficult; or they may have a negative impact on the prognosis. Due to their high rates of morbidity and mortality, ADRs are a global issue for both developed and developing nations.⁵ The World Health Organization defines pharmacovigilance as “science and activities relating to detection, assessment, understanding, and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problems.” The pharmacovigilance program has been crucial in identifying adverse drug reactions (ADRs) and removing a number of medications from the market. However, one of the main issues with pharmacovigilance programs is the underreporting of adverse drug reactions. It is advised that each nation establish its own

pharmacovigilance program due to the differences in drug availability, individual prescribing practices, drug regulatory systems, and drug response.⁸ A global database of ADR reports from all over the world is kept up to date by the Uppsala Monitoring Centre (UMC) in Sweden. In July 2010, the Central Drugs Standard Control Organization in New Delhi launched the Indian pharmacovigilance program with the aim of enhancing patient safety for the country's one billion citizens. At first, the national coordinating center (NCC) for ADR monitoring was the All-India Institute of Medical Sciences in New Delhi. To increase the program's effectiveness, the NCC was moved to the Indian Pharmacopoeia Commission in Ghaziabad, Uttar Pradesh, in April 2011 and is overseen by the UMC. The main technique for gathering ADR data is through spontaneous reporting systems, and medical undergraduates will be crucial in reporting ADRs in their future employment.⁹ Pharmacists as a health care professional could have a great role in ADR reporting both in community and hospital. Intrinsic factors such as knowledge, attitude and practice can help in understanding the importance of pharmacovigilance. Pharmacists could play an important role in ADRs reporting, as they are available to patient both in communities and hospital settings and have good knowledge about the drugs, so it is rational to involve them more in ADRs reporting.¹⁰ Therefore, this study was conducted to evaluate undergraduate students' KAP regarding pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: A cross-sectional study was carried out to evaluate the KAP amongst the Diploma in Pharmacy students of Kangleipak Medical and Nursing Institute towards ADR and Pharmacovigilance.

Duration of the study: The study was conducted from November, 2024 to January, 2025.

Inclusion and Exclusion criteria: 2nd year D. Pharm and interned students were included. Incomplete response of the questionnaire and 1st year D. Pharm students were excluded from the study.

Development of Questionnaire: The questionnaire towards KAP study on ADR and pharmacovigilance was generated from literature and adapted from the previous research studies available. The survey form is divided in four (4) sections in which the first section contains the demographic details, second section contain 8 Knowledge-based questions, third section contain

15 Attitude- based questions, fourth section contain 6 practice- based questions. The questionnaire consists of 29 close ended questions.

Statistical analysis: Descriptive statistical methods were used and data was analysed using MS excel spreadsheet. All categorical variables were presented as numbers and percentages.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

In this cross-sectional study, a total of 62 pharmacy student participants has answer fully the given KAP questionnaire. Out of which 40 are 2nd year D. Pharmacy students and 22 are D. Pharm interned students.

Table 1: Knowledge Base Questionnaire Responses

Sl. No.	Question	Correct Answer	Incorrect Answer	Don't Know	Total
1	What is an adverse event?	48 (77.5%)	5 (8%)	9 (14.5%)	62 (100%)
2	What is Pharmacovigilance?	46 (74.2%)	7 (11.3%)	9 (14.5%)	62 (100%)
		Yes	No	Don't Know	Total
3	Are you aware of the term Pharmacovigilance?	57 (92%)	3 (4.8%)	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
4	Do you know that you can directly report ADR?	45 (72.6%)	12 (19.3%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
5	Are you aware of the term under-reporting?	29 (46.8%)	17 (27.4%)	16 (25.8%)	62 (100%)
6	PvPI was officially launched in the year.	Correct answer	28 (45.16%)		
7	How can we report an ADR?	Health care professional	40 (64.52%)		
		Hospital	8 (12.9%)		
		Individually	10 (16.13%)		
		HCP & Hospital	1 (1.61%)		
		HCP & individually	1 (1.61%)		
		ALL	2 (3.23%)		
		TOTAL	62 (100%)		
8	A serious adverse reaction should be	1 day	33 (53.23%)		
		1 week	14 (22.58%)		

	reported to the regulatory body within	2 weeks	13 (20.96%)
		don't know	2 (3.23%)
		TOTAL	62 (100%)

Table 2: Attitude Base Questionnaire Responses					
Sl. No.	Questions	Should Be in Every Hospital	May Be	Not Required in Every Hospital	Total
1	What is your opinion about establishing ADR monitoring center in every hospital?	53 (85.5%)	6 (9.7%)	3 (4.8%)	62 (100%)
		Yes	No	I Don't Know	TOTAL
2	Do you think reporting of ADR is necessary?	57 (91.9%)	0	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
3	Do you think Pharmacovigilance should be taught in detail to health care professionals?	55 (88.7%)	2 (3.2%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
4	Have you any time read any article on prevention of ADRs?	36 (58.1%)	21 (33.8%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
5	Can non-medical person report ADR to a nearby healthcare professional?	51 (82.2%)	6 (9.7%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
6	Will ADR reporting ensure patient safety?	60 (96.8%)	0	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
7	Do you think reporting of an ADR is time consuming and cumbersome activity?	30 (48.4%)	23 (37.1%)	9 (14.5%)	62 (100%)
8	Do you think ADR reporting by one person can make a significant difference to the community?	44 (71%)	13 (20.9%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
9	Do you think ADR reporting will increase patient safety?	60 (96.8%)	1 (1.6%)	1 (1.6%)	62 (100%)
10	Is reporting of ADRs a part of pharmacist duty?	56 (90.3%)	4 (6.5%)	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
11	Do you believe pharmacy students could help with adverse drug reaction reporting?	57 (91.9%)	3 (4.9%)	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
12	Do you believe ADR forms are difficult to complete?	23 (37.1%)	31 (5%)	8 (12.9%)	62 (100%)
13	Do you believe that disclosing ADRs is beneficial to both patients and doctors?	45 (72.6%)	12 (19.3%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
14	Do you believe that new drugs should be closely monitored?	60 (96.8%)	0	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
15	Do you believe pharmacy students will be able to report ADRs?	55 (88.7%)	2 (3.2%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)

Table 3: Practice base questionnaire responses					
Sl. No.	Questions	Yes	No	I Don't Know	Total
1	Have you ever come across any ADR?	15 (24.2%)	43 (69.3%)	4 (6.5%)	62 (100%)
2	Have you seen an ADR reporting form?	38 (61.3%)	23(37.1%)	1 (1.6%)	62 (100%)
3	Have you ever reported an ADR/ filled an ADR reporting form?	15 (24.2%)	45 (72.6%)	2 (3.2%)	62 (100%)
4	Have you ever been trained on how to report ADR?	31 (50%)	27 (43.5%)	4 (6.5%)	62 (100%)
5	Have you ever experienced/ encountered ADR before?	13 (20.9%)	44 (71%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)
6	Are you willing to report ADR?	48 (77.5%)	9 (14.4%)	5 (8.1%)	62 (100%)

Assessment of Knowledge about ADR and Pharmacovigilance

Knowledge about ADR reporting and pharmacovigilance among the participants was assessed by eight (8) knowledge questioners and the responses are shown in the Table 1. Out of 62 participants, 48 participants i.e. 77.5% gave the correct definition of an adverse events and 74.2% participant knows the definition of pharmacovigilance whereas majority of the participants i.e. 92% are aware about pharmacovigilance. In a study conducted by K. Bharathi Priya, 80% of the participants gave correct response regarding the definition of ADR.¹¹ Similarly, in a study conducted by Jeevan Gowda B. T. et.al. 75.3% participant answered correctly but, in a study, conducted by Debasis Ray et. al. 92.9% of its participants knows the definition of pharmacovigilance.^{12,13} 72.6% of the participants knows that ADRs can be reported directly and 46.8% are aware regarding under reporting of ADR. In the study conducted by Priya K.B. et al, 70% of the student participants were aware of who can report ADR.¹¹ Only 45.16% of the participants gave correct response regarding the official year when Pharmacovigilance

programme of India was launched. 64.52% of the participants thinks that ADRs can be reported by health care professionals only, 12.9% and 16.13% thinks it can be reported through hospital only and individually respectively. However, only 3.23% knows that ADR can be reported through all the sections i.e. health care professionals, hospital and individually which is much less than 70% students stated that non-medical person can report ADR to a nearby healthcare professional in the study conducted by Priya K.B.¹¹ 20.96% of the participants knows that a serious adverse reaction should be reported to the regulatory body within 2 weeks of the event occurred whereas in the study conducted by Priya K.B., 76% students were aware that a serious adverse reaction should be reported to the regulatory body within 15 calendar days which is much more than our study.¹¹

Assessment of Attitude about ADR and Pharmacovigilance

Attitude about ADR reporting and pharmacovigilance among the participants was assessed by fifteen (15) attitude questioners and the responses are shown in the Table 2. Out of 62 participants, 53 (85.5%) participants thinks that ADR monitoring center should be established in

every hospital, whereas, 3 (4.8%) thinks that it's not required in every hospital. Similar study was conducted by Adheed Khalid Sharrad, where only 69.9% agree that ADR monitoring centre should be established in every hospital.¹⁶ 91.9% thinks reporting of ADR is necessary whereas in the study conducted by Sivadasan et al. only 42.9% think adverse drug reaction reporting is necessary.¹⁴ 88.7% of the participants think Pharmacovigilance should be taught in detail to health care professionals. 58.1% participants have time to read article on prevention of ADRs and 82.2% of the respondent thinks non-medical person can report ADR to a nearby healthcare professional whereas 9.7% thinks non-medical person cannot report ADR. In a study conducted by Adheed Khalid Sharrad, 26.5 % thinks pharmacovigilance should be taught to all health care students during their curriculum and 28.9% strongly agrees that ADRs reporting are duty of all health care professionals whereas only 21.7% have time to read article on prevention of ADRs.¹⁵ 96.8% participants think ADR reporting will ensure patient safety. 48.4% think reporting of an ADR is time consuming and cumbersome activity and 37.1% participant thinks it's not. In the study conducted by Sam, et al, 79.54% of the pharmacy students thinks its time consuming, which is much higher from our study.¹⁶ 71% of the total participant think ADR reporting by one person can make a significant difference to the community and 96.8% think ADR reporting will increase patient safety. Similarly, in the study by Priya KB, 71% students agreed the same and 95% students agreed that reporting ADR will increase patient safety.¹¹ 90.3% respondent thinks reporting of ADRs a part of pharmacist duty. 91.9% of the participant believe pharmacy students could help with adverse drug reaction reporting. 37.1% believe ADR forms are difficult to complete and only 5% feels it's not difficult to fill up the ADR form. 72.6% believe that

disclosing ADRs is beneficial to both patients and doctors whereas 19.3% thinks it is not beneficial to disclose ADR. Similarly, in the study conducted by Umashankar N et al, 95.3% agreed that ADR reporting is necessary and reporting ADR should be made mandatory.¹⁷ 96.8% participants believe that new drugs should be closely monitored and 88.7% participants believe pharmacy students will be able to report ADRs whereas in a study conducted by Venkatasubbaiah et al, 78.4% accepted the need for close monitoring of the new drugs.⁵ And in the study by Alam K et al. only 50% agreed that reporting of ADRs is a part of pharmacist duty and it is important to report ADRs leading to hospitalization.⁷

Assessment of Practice about ADR and Pharmacovigilance

Practice about ADR reporting and pharmacovigilance among the participants was assessed by six (6) practice questioners and the responses are shown in the Table 3. 24.2% of the participants, out of 62, have come across ADR. 61.3% have seen an ADR reporting form and 24.2% have filled an ADR reporting form. In a study conducted by Umashankar N et al, 94% have seen an ADR reporting form.¹⁷ 50% of the participants in our study have received training on how to fill an ADR reporting form. Similarly, 48.1% participants in the study conducted by Anu Manuel et al have received the same.¹⁸ In the study, 20.9% participants have experienced/encountered ADR in the past. Similarly, in the study conducted by Umashankar N et al 29.3% responders had witnessed an ADR. 77.5% are willing to report ADR in future.¹⁷

Limitations:

The drawback of the research is that the number of participants who were involved in this study was comparatively small.

CONCLUSION:

When toxicity and negative consequences manifest, particularly when they were previously unidentified, it is critical that they be properly documented, examined, and report to the pharmacovigilance centres. Attitudes and knowledge have a big impact on ADR reporting. Pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting would be underreported due to lack of knowledge and unfavourable opinions. To reduce ADR underreporting, seminars and conferences should be held to raise awareness and encourage a reporting culture. Pharmacists, an indispensable part of an integrated healthcare system, should play a fundamental role in reporting ADRs. This, in turn, can contribute to controlling avoidable morbidity and mortality to a great extent. Current study findings give an overall idea of the ADR reporting understanding among pharmacy students and displays their readiness to be included in the workforce as potential healthcare professional. We conclude that pharmacy students have favourable knowledge, attitude and practice on ADRs. Therefore, providing special training and educational awareness may increase the KAP of the students towards ADRs.

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